

Design concept for the sustainable use of timber in structures

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ABSTRACT: The construction sector contributes significantly to climate change and energy consumption. The decarbonization can be facilitated when energy- and resource- intensive materials such as concrete is broadly replaced with renewable materials such as timber. An extensive utilisation of timber in structures demands carefully defined and compulsory applied design rules that maximize the value of the natural resource under consideration of environmental impacts. This largely exceeds the scope of the decision rules in current structural design codes, which have been conceived with the primary objective of sufficient safety. The paper stresses the usefulness of risk-informed optimization approaches for enhancing the decision scope of these rules with consideration of the environmental performance of structures. Taking widely implemented life cycle assessment approaches as a basis, it is discussed how existing optimization frameworks could be modified to this end, with emphasis on the global warming potential of timber structures.

KEYWORDS: LCA, Sustainability, Risk-informed optimization, Timber, Structural reliability

1 INTRODUCTION

Material and energy crisis, along with concerns about rapid climate change, enhance the need of pursuing a more sustainable future. The construction sector plays a fundamental role in this. In Europe, buildings contribute to about 36% of CO₂ emissions and 40% of total energy consumption (European Commission, 2020). One way to reduce the environmental burden of buildings is to replace emission-intensive structural materials, such as concrete and steel, with renewable and nature-based materials, such as timber and timber-based products whenever viable. In addition to sustainability criteria, such substitution needs to address structural safety, among other performance goals associated with structural design (e.g. serviceability, durability). The decision rules associated with these performance goals are defined in structural codes and standards, such as

the Eurocodes. In parallel, standardized guidance to the sustainability assessment of structures has been developed in recent years, often related to the life cycle assessment (LCA). However, these two fields, the development of structural decision rules, on one hand, and of LCA methodologies and tools, on the other, are usually investigated separately. In consequence of this lack of harmonization, sustainability aspects are often disregarded in structural design procedures. In the rare case that it is applied, LCA is used as post-design evaluation as a mandatory part of rather inefficient sustainability certification schemes (Hollberg et al., 2020).

An improvement of this situation may aim at integrating the life cycle thinking into the decision rules applied in daily structural design practice. Risk-informed decision approaches based on economic optimization principles appear to be an appropriate choice for this purpose, assum-

ing that an economically optimal design solution is close to the optimum from an environmental point of view. However, existing optimization approaches require modifications, to account for sustainability-specific contributions to the objective function used in the optimization process. Inspiration for such modification can stem from well established LCA procedures.

The present paper discusses how such modifications could be addressed in case of timber structures for buildings. Section 2 introduces the principles of both LCA and economic optimization of structures. An LCA case study is then conducted, which assesses and compares the global warming potential (GWP) of a timber floor system and a functionally equivalent concrete floor (section 3). On the grounds of this case study, section 4 subsequently discusses the required modifications of current risk-informed decision approaches, as a basis for developments of design rules for timber structures. The most relevant observations of the study are summarized in section 5.

2 DECISION SUPPORT TOOLS FOR SUSTAINABLE CONSTRUCTIONS

2.1 LCA of structures

Nowadays, LCA is one of the most extensively used approaches to investigate and assess the environmental impacts and sustainability potentials of a certain product (or project) throughout its life cycle. The life cycle of a product¹ generally includes all stages from resource extraction to final disposal, also known as *cradle-to-grave*.

The principles, framework, requirements and guidelines (incl. basic four phases) of LCA, are described in ISO 14040 (2006) and ISO 14044 (2006) standard. The results are usually expressed by multiple indicators, such as the GWP or abiotic depletion potential for elements (ADPE). As a comparative tool, LCA is preferably applied as early as possible at the design stage of a product.

In order to assist the implementation of LCA for structures in practice, several standards and guidance have been published in Europe since the 2000s. The life cycle stages associated with spe-

cific modules are defined in several ISO and EN standards regarding product category rules and environmental impact assessment of structures (e.g. ISO 14025, 2006; EN 15978, 2011; EN 15804, 2012), see Figure 1.

The general procedure of LCA of structures can be summarized as follows: 1) define the goal and scope of the study clearly, such as the functional unit (FU) and system boundary, as well as limitations and assumptions. For example, what is the product system being studied, which modules are included, what is the reference service life, and what are the assumptions for the end-of-life (EoL) scenarios; 2) collect the input data such as the amount of materials and energy consumed for the construction activities, transport distances from factory to gate, etc. Using commercially validated and private (i.e. from specific manufacturer) life cycle inventory databases (e.g. material and energy flows for processes such as production and transport) is the common approach; 3) select the environmental impact assessment method (e.g. *CML-IA*, *ReCiPe*) to obtain results of different environmental indicators such as GWP (kg CO₂-eq.) and ADPE (MJ); 4) interpret the results of the studied alternatives (e.g. concrete floor vs. timber floor) and compare.

When applying LCA of structures, assumptions and inputs for the module C (EoL stage, see Fig. 1) need special attention, especially when considering the requirement of reducing waste by the EU (European Commission, 2015), as environmental impact induced from this module can vary largely between different scenarios: reuse, recycling, (energy) recovery and disposal. Consequently, the benefits and loads beyond the system boundary declared in module D differ widely.

By following the above mentioned standards, construction product manufacturers can publish their own environmental product declaration (EPD), which is a public file in accordance with product category rules (PCR) (ISO 14025, 2006). The EPD contains the complete LCA results of a product *from cradle-to-grave*. Thus, an EPD can be added as a unit process in the LCI database when conducting LCA, or it can be used individually for direct comparison of environmental impacts between products. There are also EN stan-

¹Product here is a collective word, it can be a product, a process, a project, even a service.

dards specifically dealing with wood construction products, e.g. EN 16485 (2014).

2.2 Risk-informed optimization

Given its ability to explicitly account for particular conditions and circumstances, characterizing specific structural engineering problems in consideration of the uncertainties and consequences involved, risk-informed analysis has been identified as a powerful approach for consistent decision making related to engineering structures (e.g. Rackwitz, 2000; Fischer et al., 2019; Köhler, 2019). Supported by standardized guidance and recommendations for practical applications (ISO 2394, 2015), it facilitates optimized structural design such that a balance is achieved between the benefits obtained through the implementation of a decision and the associated costs. If the benefits are considered to be independent on the decision parameter p (which is normally representative of the material quantities employed, e.g. a cross-section dimension), the optimization consists in the minimization of the total costs C_{tot} . C_{tot} is constituted by the sum of the construction cost $C_c(p)$, the expected failure cost $C_f(p)$, and the expected obsolescence cost $C_{obs}(p)$, as expressed by Equation 1. Costs related to periodic inspection or maintenance are neglected in this equation, but could be incorporated straightforward (e.g. Ellingwood, 2016).

$$C_{tot} = C_c(p) + C_f(p) + C_{obs}(p)$$

with : $C_c(p) = C_0 + C_1p$

$$C_f(p) = (C_0 + C_1p + H) \frac{P_{f,1a}(p)}{i} \quad (1)$$

$$C_{obs}(p) = (C_0 + C_1p) \frac{\omega}{i}$$

In Equation 1, term C_1 expresses the marginal costs for enhancing safety through an increase of the realization of decision parameter p , while C_0 represents the part of the construction costs that is independent of p . The expected failure cost $C_f(p)$ includes the initial construction cost $(C_0 + C_1p)$ - a similar investment is expected after the failure - and a non-structural failure cost component H (e.g. costs for demolition and debris removal, compensation costs for fatalities, loss of business).

Failure costs are considered as annual expectations as a function of the annual failure probability $P_{f,1a}$ and discounted to the time t_0 when the decision is made through the annual interest rate i . Finally, the expected obsolescence cost C_{obs} respond to the assumption of continuous renewal of a decision at an annual rate $\omega = 1/T_{SL}$ (T_{SL} = service life or renewal period), with associated costs $(C_0 + C_1p)$ discounted to t_0 (Rackwitz, 2000). Costs for demolition of the structure following obsolescence are assumed to be independent on p and can be neglected.

The economic optimization based on the objective function given by Equation 1 ensures that resources are consumed optimally from the financial point of view. In addition, constraints that are consistent with the societal preferences in regard to life safety must be introduced, see e.g. ISO 2394 (2015) and Fischer et al. (2019). Moreover, environmental consequences, such as resource consumption and embodied CO₂ emissions of structures, should be explicitly considered in an optimization framework. With a few exceptions (e.g. Adhikari et al., 2020), this has not been approached by now.

3 CASE STUDY

Timber is a structural material that can be applied in various types of constructions such as multi-storey buildings, industrial halls, or bridges. In comparison with other materials such as concrete or steel, the use of timber may largely contribute to reducing environmental impact of constructions, especially in the aspect of climate change mitigation. The main advantages of using timber in construction are: 1) timber is a natural and renewable resource; 2) manufacturing timber products consumes much less energy and thus results in less emissions compared to concrete and steel; 3) biogenic carbon storage in timber products during its service life; 4) benefits from the end use of timber: after the structure is decommissioned, the timber can be e.g. incinerated for generating heat and power.

Figure 1: Life cycle stages and modules of construction works (EN 15978, 2011).

3.1 Floor systems

The present case study illustrates the environmental benefit of using timber in prefabricated floor systems of multi-storey residential buildings. For the sake of comparison, two functionally equivalent buildings locate in Helsinki, Finland are selected, with an area of about 4400 m², respectively. One is a concrete building with typical hollow-core floors, the other is a timber building having Kerto-Ripa open-box floors. Both alternatives were designed based on Eurocodes and Finnish national annexes.

3.2 Environmental impact analysis

The FU of both systems was defined as "1 m² floor element with designed service life of 50-year". The life cycle of the analysis was *cradle-to-grave*, where the benefits and loads beyond the system boundary (module D) were included. The two buildings have identical operational energy consumption and maintenance plan (Rakennusliike Reponen, 2020). Material and energy consumed in the installation of both prefabricated floors were assumed to be identical as well. Thus, for purpose of the comparison, modules A5 (construction-installation) and B1-B7 (use and operation) were equal and hence excluded. The possibility of structural failure or anticipated obsolescence during the service life period is not considered in the study.

To increase the data quality of the LCA, EPDs

of the two floor types have been collected. For the specific timber element, no EPD was available when conducting this case study, therefore the CO₂-eq. was calculated based on the EPD files from two similar products (Metsä Wood, 2013; Stora Enso, 2019). Likewise, for the concrete floor, the available EPD from a Finnish company was used (Parma, 2019).

It was assumed that the wood is originated from sustainably managed forests, as stated in the selected EPDs. The CO₂ uptake was considered as entering the product system at the production stage and released at the EoL stage. Thus, the biogenic carbon balance over the life cycle was zero (carbon-neutral). As for the EoL scenario, in line with current practice, incineration for the timber floor and recycling for the concrete floor were considered, as shown in Table 1. Both, concrete recycling and timber incineration scenarios were considered to occur immediately after dismantling the structure and only once. The results of the LCA included seven environmental impact indicators, but this paper focuses only on the GWP.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Environmental impact - GWP

The results of the case study confirm the environmental benefits of structural timber in comparison to concrete. Specifically, the GWP is lower in each life cycle stage of the timber floor, especially the manufacturing stage (module A1-A3). At the EoL (module C1-C4) stage, the dif-

Table 1: Environmental impact – GWP in (kg CO₂-eq.) /m².

Life cycle stage	Kerto-Ripa*	Concrete
Production (A1-A3)	10.4	64.6
Transport (A4)	1.1	3.3
End-of-Life (C1-C4)	7.9 (incineration)	9.5 (recycling)
Total	19.4	77.4
Benefits and loads (D)	-33.5 (incineration)	-0.6 (recycling)

* Total GWP excluding biogenic carbon of wood.

ference is far less significant. Results of module D are presented as separate values, as specified in (EN 15978, 2011). The GWP benefit (assigned in module D) from incineration of wood is significantly larger than the one from recycling of concrete, as the incineration of wood produces heat and electricity, which would avoid the impact of using carbon-intensive fossil fuels (e.g. natural gas in heat production). The relatively low benefit from concrete recycling may be caused by the low substitution efficiency when using recycled concrete aggregates. These results underline that EoL scenarios of structural components should be carefully considered, when comparing design alternatives on the basis of LCA.

3.3.2 Monetary values of GWP

Though ISO 14040 (2006) and EN 15978 (2010) state that value-based weighting (e.g. monetization) of LCA should not be used for comparative assertion that is intended for public projects, it can provide intuitive guidance for decision-makers. Several methods for quantification of environmental impacts in monetary terms, based on different criteria, can be found in the literature. In the present study, two conceptually different methods are used, which both have been applied in the construction sector (Finnveden et al., 2013, 2006). Although these methods apply to Swedish conditions, it was assumed that they fit as well in the Finnish context. In addition, monetary values for the GWP (CO₂ price) were adjusted to the year 2020 and displayed in Table 2.

Based on these two methods, CO₂ prices (Total value in Table 2) for the floor structure of the residential building considered in the case study (i.e. 4400 m²) are about: 9731 - 28766€ for the timber case; 38824 - 114769€ for the concrete floor. Such price is significantly lower than the material and installation cost of the floor structures. It has to be noted that the unit price (per m²) of a concrete floor is, in general, significantly lower compared to a timber floor. In the present case study, the ratio was nearly 40%.

However, although the monetary value of GWP takes small portion of the total cost at present, it might vastly increase within the next few decades, considering the urgent need of reducing greenhouse gas emissions globally. The trend of increasing CO₂ price in the past several years, indicates that this need has been recognised. For example, the carbon tax in Sweden increased almost five times from 1991 to 2021 (Government Offices of Sweden, 2021). Similar trends can be observed for other methods designed to quantify environmental damages, such as the social cost of carbon (SCC), which represents the net economic cost of carbon dioxide emissions or its equivalent (Nordhaus, 2017).

3.4 Discussion

LCA studies of construction works, either product or building project, are conducted under the defined FU (e.g. in the case study, 1 m² of floor system within 50-year reference period). Thereby, in order to assess the potential environmental impact for alternatives with the same FU, associated assumptions and boundary settings are inevitable. The results and conclusions of such studies should hence be cautiously evaluated, especially when aiming at extending their scope of validity beyond the specified assessment boundaries. For example, the case study indicates that timber might be highly beneficial in the aspect of GWP at the product level, under the assumption that the timber is sourced from sustainably managed forest. However, when focusing on using timber as replacement material of concrete and steel on a large scale, the need for sustainably managed forests - as assumed in the case study (see section 3.2) - becomes imperative. Otherwise, assuming timber

Table 2: Selected methods to calculate the monetary value of the GWP (values adjusted to the year 2020) (European central bank, 2021).

Method	Monetary value [€/kg]	Background
Ecovalue2012	0.337	based on willingness-to-pay (individual preference), particularly focused on Swedish condition. Note: mean value.
Ecotax02	0.114	based on taxes and fees that represent the value society puts on environmental effects of emissions and resource consumption in Sweden.

as carbon-neutral may not be possible, see e.g. EN 16485 (2014).

Besides, from a larger perspective, the selection of EoL scenarios of construction and demolition (C&D) wood would need closer examination. As assumed in the case study, incineration of the C&D wood generates heat and power, thus contributes to climate change abatement as substitution of fossil fuels. However, such wood could be also reused or recycled (section 2.1) before directly being incinerated, what would entail potential benefits: the consumption of primary materials and of process energy for the harvest and manufacturing stage is reduced, and the CO₂ could be stored in other products or structures longer while giving time for reforestation and hence expanding the biogenic carbon sequestration. Also, this is in line with the waste hierarchy defined in the EU Directive (European Commission, 2008), which favors material recovery (e.g. reuse and recycling) instead of energy recovery. On the other hand, the EU set a renewable energy target, e.g. 32% by 2030 (European Commission, 2018), which to some extent supports the wood as renewable source for energy recovery. Therefore, trade-off between reuse/recycling and incineration scenarios should be cautiously considered. Regarding the influence of different EoL scenarios, it is referred to, e.g. Niu et al. (2021). In this context, it should be mentioned that, currently used LCA methodologies for assessing the environmental performance of structures are not yet adapted to quantify the impacts and benefits related to recycling and reuse in a consistent way. Ongoing discussions mainly revolve around appropriate strategies for the allocation of such impacts and benefits to different product life-cycles and life-cycle stages. Depending on the strategy

pursued, the conclusions of an LCA might differ considerably, thereby paving the way for undesired tailor-made assessments to produce desired results (De Wolf et al., 2020).

4 OPTIMAL STRUCTURAL DESIGN

4.1 *Current situation*

As illustrated in the case study in section 3, LCA of structures enables comparative assessments of different decision alternatives with regard to their environmental performance, such as the choice of a specific construction material. Specific caveats and limitations regarding the interpretation of the results of such assessments in a wider context, i.e. by extending the application boundaries of the LCA in space and/or time, were already mentioned in section 3.4. An additional and more fundamental problem regarding a more general value judgement of such results, is that LCA standards lack acceptance criteria that would allow users to address the question if the verdict may be "sufficiently sustainable". Decisions on the sustainability of structures are subject to manifold requirements and constraints, including safety, functionality, economy and environmental performance among others. A trade-off between these attributes is required to identify optimal design decisions that comply with societal preferences on the allocation of available financial and environmental resources, e.g. for climate change mitigation. Addressing this complex challenge clearly falls outside the scope of current LCA procedures and standards.

Structural design codes and standards, which contain the decision rules for the design, operation and maintenance of structures, provide a broader perspective in this regard. Applied in daily en-

gineering practice, these decision rules prescribe the flow of structural materials throughout our entire built environment. Hence, their careful formulation is an essential means for the representation of society's willingness to invest into sustainable development (Faber, 2020). The Eurocode EN 1990 (2002), for instance, regulates structural engineering decisions on the European level, and provides compulsory decision rules for verifying compliance with requirements to safety, serviceability and durability, among others. For the convenience of code users, the underlying semi-probabilistic concept is reflected in simple decision rules suited for routine applications. Structural safety, which is the most important performance attribute of structures, is verified through a comparison of so-called design values for resistance (R_d) and load (effect) variables (E_d), as expressed by Equation 2. Formulated in terms of characteristic values for these variables and associated reliability elements \mathbf{r} (e.g. partial safety factors, load combination factors), the design values are usually defined such that the solution complies, within reasonable bounds, with a specific nominal reliability requirement. This is in general referred to as reliability-based code calibration (e.g. Sørensen et al., 1994; Köhler, 2019). For timber specific examples, see e.g. Köhler (2012).

$$E_d(\mathbf{r}) \leq R_d(\mathbf{r}) \quad (2)$$

The main challenge of such a procedure lies in the appropriate choice of the underlying assumptions and models for the calibration process. This is commonly handled on the basis of risks experienced and apparently accepted in the past. The Eurocodes recognize that the design rules provided in the code are derived on the basis of a calibration to a long experience of building tradition (e.g. Eurocode EN1990, 2002), along with the appreciation that risks associated with structural failure are reasonably low at present (Calgaro, 2001). However, while the overall level of risks associated with civil engineering structures designed to current Eurocode practices appears to be generally acceptable, previous studies have shown that such risks diverge widely, pointing to non-optimal design decisions and, hence, to inefficient allocation of resources (e.g. Tanner, 2015). In part, the sig-

nificant scatter observed may be attributed to the necessary generalization and simplification introduced in the codified design rules to facilitate their straightforward application in daily practice (Calgaro, 2001; SAKO, 1999). However, there is significant scope for improvement, which should not be ignored in future assessments of design rules (Köhler, 2019). Such assessments should also take explicitly account of sustainability related objectives, such as resource consumption and minimization of the environmental impact of structures. Its high level of detail in regard to the representation of the decision problem and the associated ability to identify more optimal design solutions, makes risk-informed decision analysis an appropriate tool for this purpose (Köhler, 2019).

4.2 Code calibration

One possible objective function for a risk-informed calibration of standardized decision rules for structural design is presented in Equation 3. The function aims at minimizing the sum of the total costs $C_{tot,j,w}$ depending on the code-regulated reliability elements \mathbf{r} (e.g. partial safety factors) over a specific set of design situations j . The formulation of $C_{tot,j,w}$ should consider the entire structural life-cycle, from construction to the renewal after obsolescence or failure. Subscript w in $C_{tot,j,w}$ indicates that weights shall be introduced to obtain a representative set of design situations that are regulated by the calibrated design rules.

$$\mathbf{r}_{opt} = \underset{j}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_j C_{tot,j,w}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (3)$$

Equation 3 addresses the sustainability from an economic point of view. The solution, which can be found numerically, should be subject to social constraints accounting for life safety. In order to introduce the environmental criteria in the calibration procedure, the total cost function (Eq. 1) should be appropriately modified, depending on both the EoL scenario and the construction material considered. The following section describes the relevant costs and benefits that should be included when addressing the GWP in risk-based optimization of timber structures. In line with current practice, incineration of the structure (mate-

rials) after the end of service life is considered. Inclusion of material recycling or reuse scenarios might be the subject of future developments.

4.3 Modified cost function

Significant amounts of CO₂-eq. emissions are attributable to the production and construction stage (see Table 1). To account for this environmental impact, the construction costs C_c in Equation 1 are increased by component $ENV_c(p)$ - see Equation 4 - which represents the socioeconomic costs of carbon emissions embodied in structures associated with consumption of energy during different processes characterizing the *cradle-to-gate* (incl. construction process) life cycle. In addition, $ENV_c(p)$ might include the cost corresponding to the amount of CO₂ stored in the timber, in case a zero biogenic carbon balance cannot be assumed. Although according to the current pricing rates, compensation costs for CO₂ appear to be small in comparison with the construction costs, their inclusion in the optimization framework generally seems important since it may provide a reasonable basis for the establishment of environmental policies in relation to structural design decisions.

$$C_c^* = C_0 + C_{IP} + ENV_c(p) \quad (4)$$

In order to emphasize the importance of the EoL stage on the environmental performance of structures, the failure cost term C_f (Eq. 1) is adapted as expressed by Equation 5, where the expenditures H , which account for all costs that occur in addition to the (re-) construction costs C_c^* (Eq. 4), have been replaced by the sum of:

- the compensation costs for fatalities (F) and loss of business (B), $H_{F,B}$;
- the End-of-Life costs $EoL_{D,W,I}$, which include costs for demolition/deconstruction and removal of debris from the site (D), waste transport and processing of materials from the failed structure (W) and their final incineration (I);
- the monetized carbon emissions ENV_{EoL} , which is allocated to the enclosed EoL processes (D, W, I);
- the benefits $(B_E + ENV_E)p$ associated with energy recovery due to the incineration process, where $B_E p$ represents the economic

benefit (e.g. exported heat and power used for district heating and electricity), and ENV_{EoL} the monetized environmental benefit (e.g. as replacement of fossil fuels).

It should be observed that the expected failure costs C_f^* as formulated only consider ultimate limit states. Costs due to the exceedance of serviceability limit states are neglected here.

$$C_f^* = (C_c^* + H_{F,B} + EoL_{D,W,I} + ENV_{EoL} - (B_E + ENV_E)p) \frac{P_{f,1a}(p)}{i} \quad (5)$$

Unlike the monetized environmental impact of the production and construction stages, $ENV_c(p)$, and the benefits $(B_E + ENV_E)p$ due to energy recovery in consequence of the material incineration, the costs related to the EoL stage, $EoL_{D,W,I}$ and ENV_{EoL} , may be assumed to be only weakly correlated with the decision parameter p . However, since $EoL_{D,W,I}$ and ENV_{EoL} are introduced as annual expectations depending on $P_{f,1a}(p)$, they are accounted for in the failure cost expression (Eq. 5). Contrarily, they can be omitted in the formulation of the expected obsolescence costs C_{obs}^* (Eq. 6). In addition to the (re-) construction costs C_c^* , the obsolescence costs take account of the benefits $(B_E + ENV_E)p$ due to energy recovery.

$$C_{obs}^* = (C_c^* - (B_E + ENV_E)p) \frac{\omega}{i} \quad (6)$$

4.4 Multi-objective optimization

Aiming at minimizing the environmental impact of structures on the grounds of economic optimization principles, appears to be reasonable if correlation between economic costs and the environmental impact may be assumed. Referring to the GWP of structures in particular, this assumption might be valid, since both material costs and GWP are correlated to the amount of material consumed, represented by decision parameter p . However, when considering calibration of decision rules based on Equation 3, the portfolio of representative design situations j , should account for different construction materials (e.g. reinforced concrete, steel, timber), with fundamentally different relationships between the material

cost and the environmental impact caused by these materials (section 3.4). Since the relatively low socioeconomic cost of structure-embodied CO₂ emissions (in relation to the construction costs) can most unlikely compensate for the large differences between the cost-emission relationships of, e.g. concrete and timber, a deviation from the cost-optimum might be expected when the objective would consist in minimizing emissions instead of costs. A multi-objective optimization, where in addition to Equation 3 an emission-based utility function is introduced, could reveal a potential trade-off.

5 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

As we hurtle towards 2030 with the common goal of combating climate change, the window of opportunity is narrowing. The construction sector is in urgent need of implementing solutions that ensure sustainable societal development. The extensive use of timber and timber based materials is one solution, since it could significantly reduce the environmental impact of constructions, compared with conventional materials such as concrete.

The LCA case study, which compared the GWP of functionally equivalent timber and concrete floor systems, underlined this feasibility. However, in practice, design decisions are often grounded on profit-oriented thinking, in many cases limited to comparison of the construction costs of different decision alternatives. As a result, incentives for the choice of (relatively expensive) timber materials might be lacking. The perspective could completely change, however, if the entire life cycle is considered in such comparisons, including the processes beyond the EoL stage of structures (e.g. energy recovery, recycling/reuse). In this case, the balance might strongly incline in favor of timber solutions as preferable decision alternative, also from an economic point of view. However, it should be cautiously proceeded, when allocating the impacts and benefits of post-EoL processes to different product life-cycles and/or life cycle stages.

While LCA enables comparison of decision alternatives in the early conceptual design stage of

structures, the detailed verification of the design is subject to the compulsory decision rules applied in structural design codes. Their well defined calibration following optimization principles seems appropriate to integrate sustainability performance of structures into their decision scope. Therefore, an objective function for a cost-based optimization of timber structures has been defined, with specific emphasis on their GWP. The function accounts for the monetized environmental impact originated from material extraction to the final incineration. Included environmental benefits are related to energy recovery and the associated replacement of fossil fuels. In addition, benefits from biogenic carbon stored in timber might also be included in the optimization framework, if considered appropriately.

Future studies should address the influence of the environmental structural performance on the cost optimum. This will also depend on the metric/method chosen for the monetization of carbon emissions, the value of which is expected to increase significantly in the coming years. Further efforts should be dedicated to the comparison of cost and emission-based optima, and to the inclusion of other environmental impacts of structures (e.g. acidification potential).

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